

LOCALIZED DAMAGE DETECTION AND STRAIN MEASUREMENT IN LAMINATED COMPOSITE MATERIALS USING INTEGRATED CARBON NANOTUBE YARN SENSORS

Jandro L. Abot¹, Kevin Wynter¹, Samuel P. Mortin¹, Huu H. Le¹, Hugo Borges de Quadros¹, Victor.
A. Casarotto¹, John Burns¹, Alex Leo¹, Alex Belk¹ and Kalayu Belay²

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, The Catholic University of America
620 Michigan Ave. NE, Washington, DC 20064, USA
Email: abot@cua.edu, web page: <http://faculty.cua.edu/abot>

²Department of Physics, Florida A&M University, USA
2077 East Paul Dirac Dr., Tallahassee, FL 32307
Email: kalayu.belay@famu.edu, web page: [http://www.physics.famu.edu/profiles.php?name=Kalayu
Belay](http://www.physics.famu.edu/profiles.php?name=KalayuBelay)

Keywords: Carbon Nanotube Fiber, Piezoresistive Sensor, Integrated and Distributed Sensing,
Damage Detection, Strain Measurement

ABSTRACT

Carbon nanotube yarns are lightweight, stiff, strong, ductile and electrically conductive fiber-like materials that exhibit a piezoresistive response. This piezoresistive characteristic of the carbon nanotube yarns is being tapped to measure strain in polymeric and laminated composite materials through resistance measurements without adding much weight or altering the integrity of the host material. Furthermore, the same principle is being used to detect damage and delamination in laminated composite materials. This paper includes the experimental results of a study about damage detection and strain measurement in laminated polymeric composite materials using carbon nanotube yarn sensors. A combination of sensor configurations including yarns stitched through the thickness direction of the composite laminate and yarns placed straight cross wide to the laminate are used to detect the presence of damage as well as its extent and propagation pattern. As the laminated composite is mechanically loaded, the yarn sensors capture instantaneously delamination as demonstrated by the resistance response. Crucially, the yarn sensors are sensitive enough to provide a significant resistance increase output that serves as an indication of an impending delamination. The determination of the exact delamination location is achieved with the straight cross-wide yarn sensors that may experience a large strain or fail as the damage nears their locations. Minor damage such as porosity or other defects are also captured as evidenced by a small increase in the resistance of the yarn sensor. Preliminary results on the measurement of strain on the surface of laminated composites show sensitivity of the yarn sensors and the significant role of the bond between the yarn sensor and the host laminated composite. Strain measurement and damage detection using carbon nanotube yarns may offer a highly adaptive, practical, and sensitive structural health monitoring method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Monitoring the structural health of composite materials and structures has been the focus of research for several decades. Non-destructive evaluation (NDE) methods include acoustic monitoring, laser vibrometry, thermal imaging, piezoresistive carbon microfiber reinforcement, X-ray, and several other techniques [1]. They offer precise information regarding the structural integrity of a laminated composite but require costly, prolonged and complex procedures that make their use impractical in many applications. Structural health monitoring (SHM) methods provide constant and immediate feedback of the state of health of a structure including potential damage [2]. SHM methods may include vibration analysis, strain gauges, fiber optic sensors, stress wave propagation techniques as well as several other methods [2]. SHM methods that utilize micro-strain sensors can capture strain

variation due to piezoresistive effects, resonance monitoring, piezoelectric effects, capacitance variation, or changes in optical properties [3].

Piezoresistive methods work on the principle of variations in strain being proportional to changes in resistance. Commonly used piezoresistive devices include metal alloy-polymeric films or metallic foil strain gauges. These strain gauges are able to capture very low fluctuations of strain with a maximum range of about 5% [3]. Similarly, semiconductor gauges rely on the piezoresistive properties of silicone and germanium correlating the change in resistance with variations of stress instead of strain [4]. Although the semiconductor gauges are less expensive, more ductile, and operate with a gauge factor up to one hundred times higher than that of metallic foil gauges, they are significantly nonlinear in operation and suffer from high temperature sensitivity [4].

Despite the advantages of the previously mentioned piezoresistive-based SHM methods, they cannot detect initiating damage in composite materials with high compaction or multifaceted construction. More critically, they fail to achieve damage detection without altering the microstructure of the composite material. An alternative method of strain monitoring and damage detection that may offer the advantages of the previously mentioned methods without their drawbacks consists of the use carbon nanotube (CNT) yarns [5-9] that are intricately integrated into the fiber reinforcements of composite materials [10-14]. The concept is that CNT yarns are integrated in a laminated composite material forming a continuous sensor circuit, and their inherent piezoresistive sensitivity would capture small amounts of strain within the host material [10-13]. Unlike other SHM methods, integrated CNT yarn sensors may offer a non-destructive, simpler, easily customizable and robust alternative of damage detection in laminated composite materials.

Delamination in laminated composites consists of the separation of their layers and represents a significant damage risk to their integrity [15]. Delamination can occur on the edge, near the surface, or in the center of the laminated composite. Typically, edge delamination occurs because of loading perpendicular to the axis of the beam near its edge. While delamination may occur during processing of the material, interlaminar normal and shear loading cases typically lead to delamination when interlaminar shear stress components, τ_{13} and τ_{23} , exceed their strength values under the maximum stress failure criterion, or when the strain energy release rate, G_{ic} , exceeds its maximum allowable value under the fracture mechanics criterion [15]. While the range in size of delamination and damage can vary drastically, it may elude the detection capabilities of most techniques that monitor change in material geometry such as metallic foil strain gauges, which are more suitable for surface strain detection, or optical fiber monitoring that requires complex equipment and data analysis. The ability of the CNT yarn sensors to detect mode II-dominated delamination in laminated composite materials had been previously shown by these authors [10]. This paper presents the results of an experimental study about the detection of delamination and minor damage including their exact location and extent using a combination of different types of integrated CNT yarn sensors. Furthermore, it provides a detailed explanation of the methodology and the mechanisms of capturing delamination using the CNT yarn sensors. In addition, initial experimental results on the strain measurement on the surface of laminated composite materials using CNT yarn sensors are also presented.

2 CARBON NANOTUBE YARN SENSOR

The CNT yarns in this study were dry-spun from the sides of 400 to 500 μm -high vertically aligned arrays composed of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) grown by water-assisted Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD) [16-19]. The CNT yarns are composed of one or three intertwined threads. The CNT yarns composed of three threads have a total diameter of about 25 μm , a density of about 0.9 g cm^{-3} , and the twist of the single thread varies between 558 and 868 m^{-1} . A Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) image of the 3-thread yarn is presented in Fig. 1a. The CNT yarns composed of one thread have a diameter of about 29 μm and a corresponding SEM image is shown in Fig. 1b. CNT yarns exhibit a piezoresistive response that depends on the exact construction of the material including the nanotube diameter, length and chirality, twist angle of the yarn, fabrication technique and other yarn characteristics [20,21]. The response of unconstrained 1-thread yarns subjected to quasi-static uniaxial tension loading exhibits a negative piezoresistivity [14]. The response of laterally constrained yarns is being determined and will be used to predict the response of the yarn sensors that are

integrated in polymeric and composite materials. This piezoresistive characteristic of the CNT yarn is being used for sensing purposes and provide real time monitoring of the structural health of a polymeric or composite material through resistance measurements [10-13].

3 DAMAGE DETECTION

3.1 Fabrication of self-sensing composite materials

The fabrication of the self-sensing laminated polymeric composite samples with the integrated CNT yarn sensors comprises three stages: CNT yarn integration into the dry fabric layers, curing of the laminated composites, and preparation of the yarn sensor circuits. It should be noted that in the case of integrating CNT yarns into a carbon fiber laminated composite, an additional step consisting of coating the CNT yarn would be necessary to prevent short-circuiting between the carbon fibers and the CNT yarns. In this study, the CNT yarns are integrated in a glass fabric/epoxy laminated composite and the following process is used to integrate the CNT yarns into the fabric reinforcement. The CNT yarn requires unwrapping from the spool and careful inspection for defects such as sharp bends or frays, which can degrade both its mechanical and electrical properties. The CNT yarn is then secured to the head of a sewing needle and securely stitched into four layers of the glass fabric, which constitute the central layers of the laminated composite consisting of six or eight layers in this study. Before the first stitch is made, an artificial delamination may be inserted between the two central layers to control the location of the initiation of delamination growth. After stitching the CNT yarns into the central layers, colloidal silver epoxy is applied at its ends to connect electrically the CNT yarns. The silver epoxy is applied in thin coats to the 3-mm-ends of CNT yarn and formed into a flat connector. Additional dry fabric layers are then added to complete the layup of the laminated composite. Fig. 1c-e show schematics of the samples containing various CNT yarn sensor circuits. An optical image of a self-sensing laminated composite sample showing the silver epoxy electrodes is presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 1: SEM images of CNT yarn used as the sensor in the self-sensing composite materials: (a) 3-thread yarn; (b) 1-thread yarn. Top view schematic configurations consisting of laminated composite samples instrumented with CNT yarn sensors: (c) single stitched yarn sensor; (d) dual stitched yarn sensor; (e) combined stitched and straight yarn sensors.

The next step in the composite fabrication process consists of the impregnation of the yarn sensor-integrated composite layers using a hand lay-up process. The polymeric phase consists of ToolFusion™, a room temperature-curing epoxy system composed of resin and hardener, which are combined in a 5:1 resin to hardener ratio. After impregnation, the layers are sandwiched between four layers of dry carbon fiber layers acting as bleeders in order to maintain an approximate 65% fiber volume fraction. The composite sample is then placed in a mold and cured under full vacuum and 480 kPa of pressure for ten hours. After the self-sensing composite sample is removed from the mold, the electrical connections are checked to make sure they are intact. At this point, more silver epoxy may be applied to the electrodes if needed.

Figure 2: Optical image of a 6-layer glass/epoxy laminated composite sample and superimposed schematics of the integrated yarn sensors including stitched ones (through layers 2-5) and straight ones (between layers 2 and 3). Wires are later connected to the electrodes for resistance measurements.

3.2 Mechanical and electrical measurements

The coupled mechanical and electrical characterization of the self-sensing composite samples requires accurate and sensitive testing equipment to capture load, displacement and resistance histories. An MTS Criterion 43, displacement-controlled mechanical testing platform fitted with a 30 kN-load cell, is used in combination with a 3-point bending fixture as shown in the schematic of Fig. 3. Loading is monitored by a Testworks4 software controller that acquires load and displacement histories data at 1 Hz. To minimize the effect of the contact resistance, the two lower supports are positioned between the electrical connections of the stitched yarn sensor circuits, thus creating a zero stress area near the electrodes throughout the entire loading process. The self-sensing composite samples are loaded at a rate of 0.2 mm min^{-1} . Electrical monitoring of the self-sensing composite samples requires a measurement system that can accommodate to the differences in the resistance ranges of each yarn sensor circuit. A National Instruments (NI) data acquisition chassis (DAQ) Model 1978 equipped with an NI 9219 card is used along with an NI 4072 digital multi-meter (DMM) mounted on an NI PXI 1033 chassis. The DMM is capable of monitoring a single yarn sensor circuit at a time with a maximum resistance range of $1 \text{ M}\Omega$, while the DAQ chassis can capture multiple yarn sensor circuits with a maximum range of $10.5 \text{ k}\Omega$. The resistance monitoring is achieved with a NI LabVIEW Signal Express software program. After the self-sensing composite sample is secured in the 3-point bending fixture, electrical connections are made using small alligator clips. The resistance history data is acquired at a rate of 1 Hz.

Figure 3: Schematic of experimental setup of self-sensing composite sample subjected to 3-point bending: side and end cross-sectional views of laminated composite beam sample instrumented with stitched and straight yarn sensors.

3.3 Damage detection results

It has been demonstrated that CNT yarn sensors integrated in laminated composite materials are able to detect delamination [10]. The following results include the details of the damage detection and its localization and progression throughout the loading process in laminated composite materials. The mechanical/electrical response of self-sensing composite samples consisting of a glass plain weave architecture and sensor configurations like the ones indicated in Fig. 1c,d is presented in Figs. 4 to 5. Fig. 4a shows the load, P , in terms of time, t , representing the load history and the resistance, R , in terms of time, t , representing the resistance history. Fig. 4b shows the delta resistance, ΔR , or the difference between the actual resistance and the initial resistance in terms of time, t , representing the delta resistance history. Delamination in the sample is identified by the sudden decrease of the maximum load in the load history curve (event A). Delamination is detected by the stitched yarn sensor as evidenced by the significant increase in the resistance and delta resistance (event B) and by the increase of the resistance to infinity (event C). The time delay between events A and B was 67 s. This delay apparently implies that the yarn sensor may not be able to capture the delamination instantaneously. However, as it can be observed in Fig. 4b, a significant change in delta resistance slope (event D) is noticeable 48 s before event A. The resistance increases by 137 Ω between events A and D, by 40 Ω between events D and B, and by 450 Ω between events B and E, where the significant increase in resistance immediately after the delamination is halted. This response of the yarn sensor demonstrates its ability to not only detect the delamination but also to anticipate it (event D) even before the load-history response of the laminated composite sample indicates it (event A). In addition, the yarn sensor was able to withstand loading well in excess of the maximum load as well as capture the delamination without its circuit ever failing. The yarn sensor failed (event C) 504 s after event A as shown in Fig. 4a.

In order to detect minor damage prior to major delamination, the self-sensing composite samples were loaded and unloaded within the elastic region [13]. A small amount of internal damage occurred and it was revealed as a load reduction of 2 N (event F) as shown in Fig. 5. It was also observed that the yarn sensor experienced an increase in the resistance of 1.2 Ω (between events G1 and G2) with a time delay of 14 s between events F and G1.

A decrease of the resistance in the yarn sensor was observed at the beginning of all the experiments where the laminated composite samples were subjected to bending loading. Therefore, the sections of

the yarn sensor in the upper portion of the beam (above the neutral axis) undergo compressive strains and those in the lower portion of the beam (below the neutral axis) undergo tensile strains. Consequently, the overall resistance of the stitched yarn sensor includes contributions to the resistance from the yarn sections under tension and from those under compression. It had been determined that the piezoresistive response of the unconstrained yarn under uniaxial tension exhibits negative piezoresistivity [14]. The piezoresistive response of the CNT yarn under uniaxial compression is currently being investigated. It is possible that the overall resistance of the yarn sensor decreases due to a net tension in the entire stitched yarn sensor at the beginning of the loading process.

Figure 4: Detection of mode II-dominated delamination in 6-layer glass/epoxy laminated composite sample using a single stitched yarn sensor configuration. (a) Load and resistance versus time curves. (b) Load and delta resistance versus time curves.

However, once the yarn sensor starts being damaged at different sections, the determined piezoresistive response of the undamaged yarn is no longer applicable and the overall resistance continues to increase regardless of the specific strain in the yarn.

Figure 5. Detection of minor damage in 6-layer glass/epoxy laminated composite sample using a single stitched yarn sensor configuration: load and delta resistance versus time curves.

The determination of the exact location of delamination and its progression in the laminated composite samples can be achieved with a configuration consisting of a combination of different yarn sensors like the one shown in Fig. 1e, which includes stitched yarn sensors and straight cross wide yarn sensors. The through-the-thickness stitched yarn sensors allow the determination of delamination but only additional straight yarn sensors parallel to the composite laminate layers and along the beam's width direction are able to detect the precise location of the delamination or the damage. Fig. 2 shows an image of a fabricated self-sensing composite sample containing both types of yarn sensors. It is worth mentioning that the straight yarn sensors were configured for two point probe measurements but the stitched sensors were set up for four point probe measurements so that contact resistance does not play any role. It is worth mentioning that damage detection based on a significant delta resistance increase does not need to rely on minute resistance measurements and thus two probe measurements are deemed appropriate and sufficient. Fig. 6 shows the load and resistance histories of all the yarn sensor circuits.

The two stitched yarn sensors, indicated as continuous and dotted red lines, respectively (stitched yarn sensor circuits #1 and #2) in Fig. 6, show sensitivity to the deformation throughout the entire loading process of the laminated composite sample as indicated by the initial resistance decrease followed by a resistance increase. They both detect the delamination as shown by the corresponding jumps in the resistance and the time delay between these events (B1 and B2) is 151 s. This time delay could be attributed to a slight asymmetric growth of the initial delamination. In these particular experiments, four straight yarn sensors were placed as indicated in the inset of Fig. 6. All the straight yarn sensors increase their resistance output during the entire loading process and delamination

progress. Straight yarn sensor circuit #4, indicated as a continuous brown line in Fig. 6, exhibits a resistance increase of about 4.3Ω before failing when the delamination reaches its location at about 280 s before the delamination reaches the first stitched yarn sensor. The two outer straight yarn sensors, indicated as a continuous green line (straight yarn sensor circuit #5) and as a continuous yellow line (straight yarn sensor circuit #6) in Fig. 6, exhibit an increasing resistance of several ohms over time. However, these outer straight yarn sensors do not fail because the delamination does not reach them before the sample experienced a significant deformation and the test was stopped. The yarn sensor that is underneath the load application point (straight yarn sensor circuit #3) in Fig. 6 tends to exhibit significant noise due to the transversely compressive load exerted at the center of the beam.

Figure 6: Localized detection of major delamination using a configuration of combined stitched and straight yarn sensors in 6-layer glass/epoxy laminated composite sample: load and delta resistance versus time curves.

Many experiments were run using shorter beam configurations and it was observed consistently that the straight yarn sensor closest to the delamination fails first and subsequently the other straight yarn sensors fail as the delamination propagates and reaches their locations. The straight yarn sensors are being placed between the central layers of the laminate, and are thus not subject to bending stresses but only shear stresses. The correlation between the stress level and the resistance of the yarn sensor requires further investigation.

4 STRAIN MEASUREMENT

4.1 Fabrication of self-sensing composite materials

In order to measure the strain on the surface of laminated composite materials, corresponding samples were instrumented with a metallic foil strain gauge and two CNT yarn sensors. The CNT yarns consisted of a one-thread with a diameter of $40 \mu\text{m}$ and were mounted on each side of a metallic

foil strain gauge (Micro-MeasurementsTM EA-05-125AD-120). Three different bonding configurations were selected to bond the yarn sensors to the laminated composite sample including a tape adhesive, a spray adhesive, and a liquid adhesive. Some samples had one CNT yarn bonded to the sample with 3M super 77 spray adhesive on one side, and one CNT yarn bonded with tape adhesive on the other side (Fig. 7a). Other samples had one CNT yarn mounted with spray adhesive spray on one side and a CNT yarn bonded with M-Bond 200 liquid adhesive (Micro-MeasurementsTM adhesive used to bond metallic foil strain gauges) on the other side (Fig. 7b). All CNT yarn sensors had an active gauge length of 1 mm and were placed parallel to the metallic foil strain gauge. To mount the CNT yarn using tape adhesive, a piece of tape was cut to be 1mm-long. This tape was then flipped sticky side up and the CNT yarn was laid over it along the 1 mm length using tweezers. The tape was then gently pressed against the left side of the sample so that the CNT yarn was parallel with the metallic foil strain gauge. A 1 mm-long mounting area was left unmasked so that adhesive could be applied. For the bonding using the spray adhesive, the adhesive was first sprayed into a cup and then applied to the sample using a wooden stick to achieve a more consistent adhesive distribution. The liquid adhesive was applied to the laminated composite sample using the same process as the mounting of the metallic foil strain gauge except that the catalyst was not applied. After the adhesive was applied onto the laminated composite sample, the masking tape was removed and the CNT yarn was laid into the adhesive parallel to the metallic foil strain gauge. Two dabs of a rubberized conductive epoxy (Bare ConductiveTM) were applied to the CNT yarns to create the electrodes for the four point probe measurements.

4.2 Mechanical and electrical measurements

The instrumented laminated composite samples were subjected to uniaxial tension using the MTS Criterion 43, which provided the load and the displacement data. The electrical measurements were made using the same devices and procedure described in section 3.2. The experimental setup including the instrumented sample is shown in Fig. 7c,d. The first set of samples were subjected to eight consecutive tests to strain levels of up to 0.2 % or 0.4 %, with loading rates varying between 0.02 and 0.04 mm min⁻¹ and an acquisition rate of 1 Hz.

Figure 7: Optical images of: (a) instrumented sample with CNT yarns bonded with tape adhesive and spray adhesive; (b) instrumented sample with CNT yarns bonded with liquid adhesive and spray adhesive; (c) experimental setup; (d) close-up of experimental setup.

4.3 Preliminary strain measurement results

Preliminary results are now available and the corresponding observations are described next. All CNT yarn sensors exhibited a monotonic piezoresistive response regardless of the bonding adhesive. The response of the yarn sensors bonded with tape adhesive showed negative piezoresistivity while the yarn sensors bonded with spray adhesive or liquid adhesive exhibited positive piezoresistivity. The negative piezoresistive response of the yarn sensor bonded with the tape adhesive may be attributed to the CNT yarn' slipping from the tape and this response is consistent with that previously observed for the unconstrained CNT yarn under tension [14]. The repeatability of the acquired resistance data was

quite poor and the unloading of the CNT yarn led to either tape wrinkling or a change in the CNT yarn structure, which were all deemed unacceptable. Perhaps mounting the CNT yarn without the tape adhesive and leaving it laterally unconstrained would provide a more consistent response. The piezoresistive response of the yarn sensor bonded with the spray adhesive was monotonic, relatively linear but unrepeatably. This may be attributed to the non-uniform distribution of the spray adhesive particles, which led to sections of both bonded and un-bonded CNT yarn. The piezoresistive response of the yarn sensor bonded with the liquid adhesive exhibited a linear response and the data was repeatable after many cycles. This repeatability may be attributed to the uniform bonding throughout the entire length of the CNT yarn. New sensor configurations including bundles and foil-like designs are being considered along with new experimental and computational modeling programs [22].

5 CONCLUSIONS

An experimental study was conducted to evaluate the ability of piezoresistive-based, integrated and distributed carbon nanotube yarn sensors to detect minor damage and delamination in laminated composite materials, determine the specific location of the damage and delamination, and further understand the yarn sensors' response in this monitoring methodology. The study included monitoring the growth of preset delamination defects and randomly appearing damage during loading of glass fabric polymeric laminated composite samples using integrated yarn sensors. The study showed the ability of the yarn sensors to not only capture the delamination but also anticipate it as exhibited by a significant increase in the resistance of the stitched yarn sensors ahead of the delamination. The sensitivity of the yarn sensors is also exhibited by their ability to detect minor damage as demonstrated by a slight increase in their resistance immediately after the load experiences a small and sharp reduction. Despite the sensitivity of the integrated yarn sensors, they are able to sustain significant deformation and fail, as exhibited by their resistance increase to infinity, when the host laminated composite fails. The exact location and progression of a delamination was determined by additional straight yarn sensors that yield a higher resistance output when the delamination reaches their specific locations. The measurement of strain using carbon nanotube yarns is also feasible although the sensor configuration and bonding technique to the host material play a significant role and need to be better understood. All the previous findings contribute to the further investigation into the viability of a multi-sensor network to monitor an entire designated area and pinpoint the exact location of damage. These carbon nanotube yarn sensors provide good piezoresistive response to loading without compromising the integrity of the laminated composite, offering thus the potential for developing a highly adaptive, practical, and sensitive structural health monitoring method. However, many questions remain to be answered through more research. Crucially, it must be determined if the damage or delamination actually reaches the location of the yarn sensor when a significant resistance increase is measured.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank the following students at The Catholic University of America (CUA): Tareq Alesh, Angeline Bajar, Michael-David Lamos, Edward Mitchell and Jason Quisberth for their support to the experimental sections of this study; and the machinist at CUA, Don Smolley, for the fabrication of testing fixtures. Abot and Belay acknowledge the financial support from AFOSR through Grant FA9550-10-1-0040 with program officer Dr. David Stargel.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Hellier, *Handbook of nondestructive evaluation*, ed. 2, McGraw-Hill, Westminister, 2012.
- [2] C. Boller, F. -K. Chang and Y. Fujino, *Encyclopedia of structural health monitoring*, Wiley, Chichester, 2009.
- [3] J. W. Dally and W. F. Riley, *Experimental stress analysis*, ed. 3, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1990.
- [4] S. Middelhoek and S. A. Audet, *Silicon sensors*, Delft University Press, Delft, 1994.

- [5] K.L. Jiang, Q.Q. Li and S.S. Fan, Nanotechnology: spinning continuous carbon nanotube yarns. *Nature*, **419**, 2002, pp. 801.
- [6] M. Zhang, K.R. Atkinson and R.H. Baughman, Multifunctional carbon nanotube yarns by downsizing an ancient technology, *Science*, **306**, 2004, pp. 1358–1361.
- [7] N. Behabtu, M.J. Green and M. Pasquali, Carbon nanotube-based neat fibers, *Nano Today*, **3**, 2008, pp. 24–34.
- [8] W. Lu, M. Zu, J.–H. Byun, B.–S. Kim and T.–W. Chou, State of the art of carbon nanotube fibers: opportunities and challenges, *Advanced Materials*, **14**, 2012, pp. 1805–1833.
- [9] J. Park and K.–H. Lee, Carbon nanotube yarns, *Korean Journal of Chemical Engineering*, **29**, 2012, pp. 277–287.
- [10] J.L. Abot, Y. Song, M. Sri Vatsavaya, S. Medikonda, Z. Kier, C. Jayasinghe, N. Rooy, V.N. Shanov and M.J. Schulz, Delamination detection with carbon nanotube thread in self-sensing composite materials, *Composites Science and Technology*, **70**, 2010, pp. 1113–1119.
- [11] J.L. Abot, M.J. Schulz, Y. Song, S. Medikonda and N. Rooy, Novel distributed strain sensing in polymeric materials, *Smart Materials and Structures*, **19**, 2010, pp. 085007.
- [12] C. Jayasinghe, W. Li, Y. Song, J.L. Abot, V.N. Shanov, S. Fialkova, S. Yarmolenko, S. Sundaramurthy, Y. Chen, W. Cho, S. Chakrabarti, G. Li, Y. Yun and M.J. Schulz, Nanotube responsive materials, *MRS Bulletin*, **35**, 2010, pp. 682–692.
- [13] J.L. Abot, K. Wynter, S.P. Mortin, H. Borges de Quadros, H.H. Le, D.C. Renner and K. Belay, Localized detection of damage in laminated composite materials using carbon nanotube yarn sensors, *Journal of Multifunctional Composites Special Issue: Novel Sensing Techniques and Approaches in Composite Materials* (submitted).
- [14] J.L. Abot, T. Alesh and K. Belay, Strain dependence of electrical resistance in carbon nanotube yarns, *Carbon*, **70**, 2014, pp. 95–102.
- [15] I. M. Daniel and O. Ishai, *Engineering mechanics of composite materials*, ed. 2, Oxford, New York, 2006.
- [16] M. Schulz, V. Shanov and Z. Yin, *Nanotube superfiber materials: changing engineering design*, Elsevier, Oxford, 2014.
- [17] C. Jayasinghe, T. Amstutz, M.J. Schulz and V. Shanov, Improved processing of carbon nanotube yarn, *Journal of Nanomaterials*, **309617**, 2013, pp. 1–7.
- [18] M. Miao, Yarn spun from carbon nanotube forests: production, structure, properties and applications, *Particuology*, **11**, 2013, pp. 378–393.
- [19] N. Behabtu, C.C. Young, D.E. Tsentalovich, O. Kleinerman, X. Wang, A.W.K. Ma, E.A. Bengio, R.F. ter Waarbeek, J.J. de Jong, R.E. Hoogerwerf, S.B. Fairchild, J.B. Ferguson, B. Maruyama, J. Kono, Y. Talmon, Y. Cohen, M.J. Otto and M. Pasquali, Strong, light, multifunctional fibers of carbon nanotubes with ultrahigh conductivity, *Science*, **339**, 2013, pp. 182–186.
- [20] A. Lekawa-Raus, K.K.K. Koziol and A.H. Windle, Piezoresistive effect in carbon nanotube fibers, *ACS Nano*, **8**, 2014, pp. 1114–1124.
- [21] A. Lekawa-Raus, J. Patmore, L. Kurzepa, J. Bulmer and K. Koziol, Electrical properties of carbon nanotube based fibers and their future use in electrical wiring, *Advanced Functional Materials*, **24**, 2014, pp. 3661–3682.
- [22] J.L. Abot, C.Y. Kiyono, G.P. Thomas and E.C.N. Silva, Strain gauge sensors comprised of carbon nanotube yarn: parametric numerical analysis of their piezoresistive response, *Smart Materials and Structures* (in press).